

Rac-3g

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-112-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	09012
Vial:	43	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 112 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	16.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	9/1/2021 2:17:46 PM CST		
Date Processed:	9/1/2021 3:03:15 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.876	1394583	50.02	115997
2	12.848	1393522	49.98	76878

Asy-3g (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-113-3-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	09013
Vial:	72	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 113 3
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	16.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	9/1/2021 2:42:19 PM CST		
Date Processed:	9/1/2021 3:00:39 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.908	1299589	4.17	106995
2	12.872	29880473	95.83	1629167

Asy-3g (KR)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-113-1-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	09012
Vial:	42	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 113 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	16.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	9/1/2021 1:56:52 PM CST		
Date Processed:	9/1/2021 3:01:53 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.889	797483	4.05	66823
2	12.847	18884990	95.95	1037535